

The Queer of Queers: Debunking the Stereotype in Carlo Vergara's Zsazsa Zaturannah

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Introduction

In the publication of Kenkoy in Liwayway in the late 1920s, the public was caught by surprise with a new form – “graphic images and strange-looking balloons in frames that must be read from left to right to get the story (Reyes, 2012). This problematized the meaning and function of reading as the public is used to seeing printed words in volumes (Reyes, p. 151). Komiks gained strength and popularity because more readers realized how wide the array of topics and subjects could be used as material for this form. It is both the source of aliw and aral for millions of Filipinos through decades (Gonzaga, et al, 2010). The form invites readers of all ages to take a peak and enjoy the genre because of its friendly approach. Its graphics and letterings help readers understand the story more and it gives them a fluid run of images that is happening in each panel. Komiks also promote openness to writers and readers because topics such as homosexuality, religion, macabre and androgyny are tackled in this genre without much censorship, considering the images shown. The said topics were often seen as “taboo” in the Philippines, considering that the population is mostly Catholic. Komiks is a great avenue for educating the younger generation and interjecting komiks in the academe would help students understand these issues and topics more. It is through komiks that issues are to be discussed in order to raise awareness that these taboos exist and that it should be talked about to demystify the issue.

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Much like any other form, komiks also found itself in a great decline both in readers and writers. Due to this decline, komiks was made to go through a transformation which enabled it to gather bigger audience through films and teleseryes. The characters, situations, costumes, weapons and other gadgets used by both heroes and villains were also modernized in order to cope with the times and to entice younger viewers (Reyes, p. 153). The actors and actresses who portrayed the roles of the heroes and heroines were also young stars with big fandom to lock-in a sure number of viewers because of these artists' big following crowd. The internet also became an aid in reviving komiks. It allowed readers from different walks of life to appreciate stories and graphics of published and unpublished komiks writers for free. Platforms like blogspot.com gave way for digitized comics to be seen and be interpreted by the public. It is also a platform where the creators get to interact with the readers through comments, and the suggestions by the readers may be incorporated in the next episodes or chapters of the komiks.

Analysis and Discussion

This paper will be working on two books of Carlo Vergara's Zsazsa Zaturannah, namely, *Ang Kagila-gilalas na Pakikipagsapalaran ni Zsazsa Zaturannah* (Collected Edition) and *Zsazsa Zaturannah Sa Kalakhang Maynila* (Book 1), which are komiks. The academe used to ignore the fact that komiks do not only tackle about superheroes and villains, instead, the country's history, folklore and literature. Slowly, the academe opened itself to the “possibility of examining the komiks as an artifact worthy of analysis and theorizing” (Reyes, p. 154). It would also be delving on the perfection of gender that Ada/Zsazsa is given, being able to shift from one gender to another, thus breaking stereotypes of both gender heteronormativity and superhero characteristics.

Komiks is unthinkable without our recognizing its deep indebtedness to the rich lore of the common people, the texts which our forefathers sought to make sense of their lives and thus engage in complicated reality. It is precisely this tight connection between modern artifact and traditional texts which have accumulated numerous meanings in the collective psyche that ought to be investigated (Reyes, p. 155).

Ada/Zsazsa's connection with the people in the community are very evident because much like the people in the community, Ada/Zsazsa is also part of those living in the poverty line. She owns a parlor that allows her to live on a day to day basis. Scenes like when Ada/Zsazsa's and her assistant, Didi, would sit outside the parlor when there is no customer to gossip about the "goings" on in the community, the pustahan that happened when she Ada/Zsazsa was about to fight the Amazonistas, allowed the readers to feel that Ada/Zsazsa is indeed a part of the community. This enriches the character more as Ada/Zsazsa was not just a representation of herself but of the community.

The humor that is inculcated in Carlo Vergara's work "was created because the situation being depicted showed some reversal and in favor of the dispossessed, the ordinary audience of such tales" (Reyes, p. 157). Ada/Zsazsa's humor was very evident in her language – the usage of gay lingo. Humor may also be seen in circumstances when she was fighting Queen Femina Suarestellar Baroux, at the same time discovering Ada/Zsazsa's own powers. The humorous acts of Ada/Zsazsa gave her an edge against the opponent, especially when she started grabbing Queen Baroux's hair, despite Ada/Zsazsa's ignorance on her own capabilities. Through humor, the underdog – Ada/Zsazsa – is given more life and lambasting the enemy, the Amazonistas, may also be one of the techniques to win the fight. It infuriates the enemy more to the point of the enemy not being able to concentrate on the fight at hand. In various degrees, the heroes represented or symbolized desired goals of the community. Thus, epics were constructs produced not only to entertain but to consolidate and reinforce the values of the community. These narratives constituted their exploits that would eventually lead to a transformation, within himself or within the community (Reyes, p. 158).

Ada/Zsazsa lived in a poverty-stricken community, and everyone's goal is to be able to find a way to live a well-off life. Ada/Zsazsa was the one given the opportunity to experience greener pastures. This can be seen when Ada/Zsazsa was offered a contract by YOY25, a TV network, which would make her a well-known premiere superhero. The "transformation" by Ada/Zsazsa was both obvious and subtle. The obvious transformation was when Ada becomes a woman after swallowing Zaturannah. Ada then transfigures to Zsazsa, a woman with supernatural strength, power, and beauty; the total opposite of Ada. The more subtle change in Ada/Zsazsa was that she also allowed herself to love and to be loved (Fig. 1) despite the fact that she experienced trauma and violence from her past lover. The community also transformed from being selfish individuals (Fig. 2), when they did not want to help Zsazsa kill the mumu and just wanted to stay inside the church to pray, to a united community that helped Zsazsa defeat her enemies through support and man power (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Komiks provided the readers an escape which "pointed to a world we would like to see as contrasted to the world as it was during the period – fallen, unredeemed, in turmoil, and cut-off from moorings" (Reyes, p. 163). Ada/Zsazsa may be a reflection of those who want to escape the reality that most Filipinos still have a hard time accepting the LGBTQ community.

Ang Kagila-gilalas na Pakikipagsapalaran ni Zsazsa Zaturannah and Zsazsa Zaturannah Sa Kalakhang Maynila is about a gay beautician named Ada/Zsazsa who was chosen by the stone Zaturannah in order to save human kind (or just his barangay). Ever since Ada/Zsazsa knew what powers he had, he fought a couple of battles namely: 1) the battle with a giant frog; 2) the battle with the mumu; 3) the battle with the Amazonistas, a group of women from Planet X (xxx) who wants to take over planet earth; and 4) the battle with a giant cockroach. These battles actually remind most of the audience about Darna, an orphan girl who was given a powerful stone to transform to a superhero after she shouts "Darna!"

Both characters were seen as nobody in their communities and were chosen through a divine providence of some sort, to have the privilege of saving the people from harm with the use of a magical stone. The difference is, Narda is a heterosexual female and is still a heterosexual female when she transforms to a superhero Darna, while Ada/Zsazsa is a homosexual male and turns into a female. The stone zaturnnah made Ada/Zsazsa to possess a female body, while he maintains everything he is – the way he talks, thinks and feels as it may be seen in her dialogues:

“DIDI! BABAE AKOOH! ... Hindi nga, Didi! Tignan mo, o! BABAE AKOOOH!... Shet, Didi! Totoo nga! Makapangyarihanang bato! Isa na akong girl! ... Anong hindi? Tignan mo... May nota ba ako?? WALAAAH!”

Some Realities of Homosexual Males

The graphic novel does not only depict some of the realities that the LGBT community faces in everyday life. According to Butler (1999), “policing gender is sometimes used as a way of securing heterosexuality.” Policing someone may be seen through continuously criticizing a person’s sexuality; by calling him/her names like juding, tibo, beki, salot sa lipunan, etc. This act of criticizing and questioning one’s gender, especially if it goes against heteronormative beliefs, somewhat gives the critic a sense of affirmation that his/her heteronormative gender is more superior. One example that is associated to policing gender in the graphic novel is the inability to accept homosexual children. Ada/Zsazsa is an only child and his father despised him – even after death – as Ada/Zsazsa’s father’s corpse said:

“Shino ikaww? ‘Alaa kung anak shnababayehh ... Adrian? Ang binabayehh? ... Kahangan! Alaa kung anak shnabinabayehh! Ishasiyang shalot sa buhay nameng mag-asawaah! Dahel sa lintekshna ‘yun, hende na kame nakabuo shngibenganaksh! Hindi na bali kong na bigyan akung apo, ngunit daig pa niya ang bilas kung kumerengkenng! Mabuti pang patayin ko na sarilih kohh! Ishasiyang salot! Naririnig mo ba akohh? Shalot siya! Ishang SHALOT!!”

Ada/Zsazsa has been seen by her parents as a curse to their family. Being an only child and becoming a homosexual male, his parents saw it as something bad, something to be ashamed of, something to blame everything to – even his parents’ not being able to rear another child. This situation of Ada/Zsazsa’s relationship is somewhat true in reality. The homosexual male children are seen as a disgrace to the family. The same situation is also described in the song Sirenaby Gloc9:

“Sa tuwing na nonood ng liga laging natutulala / Kahit di pumapasok ang bola ako’y tuwang-tuwa / Kahit kinalyo na sa tapang, kasiganunalamang / Akong paluin ng tubo kahit kinakalawang / Tama namanitay, di napo ako pasaway / Di kona po isusuotang lumang daster ni inay / Kapag ako’y naiyak ay sumusugod sa ambon / Iniisip ko nalamang na baka ako’y ampon / Kasi araw-araw na lamang ay walang humpay na banat / Ang ina abot ng ganda kong pang-ilalim ng dagat.”

Unlike the situation in the song, Ada/Zsazsa was never seen battered by his father since his father was introduced in the komiks as a zombie. Because of the father’s hatred toward Ada/Zsazsa as seen in his dialogue, it may be implied that Ada/Zsazsa might have suffered violence when he was a child. Even if the father’s violence was just implied and not vividly shown in the graphic novel, the situation given in the song is true for most of the homosexual males in the Philippines. Violence is somewhat connected to being a homosexual male, because it steps on the ego of males, the father of Ada/Zsazsa for example. It may pose a great question for them as to why their son has to be gay, when in fact the son is already a member of a privileged sex; why their privileged son, culturally and traditionally speaking, chose to stoop down to the level of the females. These questions are asked by the fathers to themselves, thus resorting to violence because it is a direct indication of masculine power; the power that a son would have if he was a heterosexual male.

Another instance as to why violence is connected to homosexuality is because homosexuality has been seen as a psychiatric disorder for decades, and even if it was removed from paper as a disorder, people’s minds are still set to that ideology. Violence is one of the most handy ways for people to use against homosexuals because they think that it would give them enlightenment or catharsis that what they are doing is wrong and that their sexuality is wrong. Another example that the graphic novel tackled is the impossibility of finding true love – for Ada/Zsazsa. That is, Ada/Zsazsa had a traumatic experience with his ex-lover named Lester. Lester inflicted violence over Ada/Zsazsa as Lester shouts:

“Tumigil kanga! Ang arte mo! ... Paano mo ako pinaligaya, eh baklaka lang? ... MAHAL? Anong alam mo sa pagmamahal? Isa lang ang hinahanap ninyo sa mga lalaki, ‘di ba? Basta mapuno yang bibig ninyo, masaya na kayo! ... ‘Tangina kang bakla ka! Eh kung kamaoko tsupain mo?! Pasalamat ka pwede kanang tsumupang limang elepante salaki ng bunganga mo! HAHAAH! ... Ipasok mo ito sa malandi mong utak. Walang magmamahal sa’yo at walanang magtitiis sa’yo! Simula ngayon, kahit sinong lalaking dadaan sa bunganga mo, lolokohin ka! Bibiguin ka! At kung sabik kang makatikimulingburat... MAGKAROON KA MUNA NG PUKE!”

This rendered Ada/Zsazsa hurt and bitter about love. Ada/Zsazsa has a new lover, Dodong, but the things that Lester did to Ada/Lester kept him cold and uninviting. Nightmares about what had happened to Ada/Zsazsa when he was with Lester kept on bothering him, thus being skeptic about Dodong.

In reality, this is somewhat true as well. Gays have been stereotyped as sexual addicts, to the point that all they want from their boyfriends is sex, and that they are not capable of true love. A lot of heterosexual males, if you may call them that, act as boyfriends to homosexual males in order to get money from them. They allow themselves to have sexual intercourse with gay men, and in return, these gay men would give their boyfriends allowances for food, clothes, etc.

Some “big time” gay men would even call their boyfriends “scholars” because the amount of money they give to their boyfriends is almost the same rate as paying their tuition, unless they really are making them study. Not all gay men experience this, but this is what society has stereotyped them and their situations. Ada is an embodiment of that stereotype, which is later on broken by the end of the graphic novel.

Homosexuality and Alienation

Ada/Zsazsa did not only face weird creatures, but she also faced a group of women that was patterned after the Spice Girls because of its production-number-like introduction and poses called the Amazonistas. The Amazonistas are a group of women from Planet X (xxx) who are man-haters and want to take over planet earth. These alien creatures represent not only the alienation of homosexual males, but also the treatment towards them. These Amazonistas metaphorically states that homosexual males, like Ada/Zsazsa, should be alien as well. This is the situation nowadays, even if it is more subtle. Homosexual males are being alienated, ignored and kept out of place. Most of the members of the LGBTQ community feel the same way: isolated from the world since they are considered different, not part of the binary oppositions, so it would be better to be with the same people so they would not feel the isolation when they are away from their support group.

These women also represent the way society perceives homosexual males. People want them to perish, to die, as what the Amazonistas want to happen to Ada/Zsazsa, because they have been seen as diseases of the community. Since the Philippines mostly consist of Catholics, homosexuality is seen as a sin. Those conservative Catholics could not accept the fact that this community exists and they try to lecture them and do everything – even resort to violence – just for the sake of converting them and making them “turn back to God” by being a heterosexual male.

Homosexual Stereotypes

In the Philippines, the most prominent idea of gays or the “bakla” is an “effeminate, cross-dresser, loud parlorista, gossip writer” (Corpuz, retrieved from <http://images.gmanews.tv/pdf/aseanconf/CORPUZ%20david.pdf>), but there are a few other variations like the closet gay and the macho gay. The two later images of the “baklais” used in order to mask one’s sexuality. The closet gays are those that pretend to be straight males, because they are afraid of getting rejected and discriminated. Usually, the fear of how one’s parents would react is one of the reasons why homosexual males still choose to be closet gays. As for the macho gay, these are the gay men who usually work as macho dancers in gay bars. These macho dancers “look real masculine and tough from afar, but when you begin to interact with them, they show inclinations to the same sex” (Tagudina, 2012).

According to Katherine Franke, as quoted by Butler, “gay people, for instance, may be discriminated against in positions of employment because they fail to ‘appear’ in accordance with accepted gendered norms” (p. xiii). Ada is a parlorista and he did not even try to look for a different job that could help him earn more money. No other job was offered to Ada, except only when he transformed to Zsazsa, and then YOY25 offered her a deal. Ada’s repetitive mention of “bakla ako” in the beginning of the graphic novel somewhat convinces herself that being a parlorista is the only thing he can do, nothing more.

Ada/Zsazsa portrays a parlor gay stereotype role in the graphic novel. Working at a salon is not the only requirement to be called as such, but the parlor gay stereotype focuses on how a homosexual male looks. One is called a parlor gay if he walks in flashy clothes most, if not all the time, with make-up brighter than his clothes, owning every color in his eye shadow collection, and accessories hanging from where it could hang, as they walk around the corners of the streets, pretending that it is a cat walk. Parlor gays are also said to be very fluent in gay lingo. All throughout the graphic novel, Ada is perceived as this parlor gay, because of how he dresses himself. As it may be seen in the graphics of Zsazsa Zaturannah, Ada uses feminine clothes during normal days, a feminine top with simple designs, but his fashion sense may be seen in Book 1, Zsazsa Zaturannah sa Kalakhang Maynila. As she was travelling to Manila, she was wearing a top, a bandana of some sort over his head, and butterfly-shaped sunglasses. As Zsazsa, he is usually seen with clothes as small as how lingerie fits the body. Zsazsa, still being gay inside a feminine body, wears sexy skimpy clothes because the only time she could wear such things is when he is Zsazsa, considering that she has everything to flaunt. Ada/Zsazsa is an expert in gay lingo, which may be proved as she sings:

“Me is looking for you Manila... Your birit is so sarap to the tenga... At yong dyipnis that are flying flying... With your shushukis they are so exciting... Yapusin mo ako Manila... Pangako mo na wilch kang mag-ago-go! ... Ang shurvah shurloong Manila... Ang beng si bengshoong Manila... Anhin ko pa ang Isteyytss!!” (Vergara, 2012)

Ada/Zsazsa’s being a master of the craft of gay lingo and being a cross-dresser, she goes with the definition of a parlor gay; thus, making him part of the stereotype of a parlor gay.

Debunking the Stereotype

Gays are often seen as loud and proud homosexual males, but are also weak and fragile. Gays are definitely gay; they are always seen happy, loud and laughing, but a lot of people nowadays overlook the fact that they, too, have emotions and that they, too, get hurt as well. Ada/Zsazsa, is one of those parlor gays who was hurt, as it may be seen to her graphic image that caught his reaction for when his father called him a curse to their family. It may also be seen when his ex-lover, Lester was punching him, and the bitterness resonates long after the scene itself.

Ada/Zsazsa subverts the images of stereotype gays, given that they are weak and fragile. Ada/Zsazsa is put on a pedestal and is given the power to be a superhero. Gays have always been appealing for their rights as humans, because they are continuously discriminated and seen as a community disorder. Factors that make homosexual males are treated as such may be because of: 1) the overt Catholicism in the Philippines, which sparks the hindrance of same-sex relationships for it is seen as immoral, and 2) because the Philippines is a patriarchal country, “every man should be true to what he is perceived to be: masculine and virile” (Tagudina, p.6) Ada/Zsazsa being a superhero, suggests that he may be the hope of the homosexual males. Given the power that Ada/Zsazsa has because of the stone zaturannah, he may liberate and empower homosexual males, since he is in power – he has a high position because the community adores him for saving their barangay. This position in the society, as dictated by the mass, is a start on reaching the aspirations of gay men being free.

For Butler, “gender can be rendered ambiguous without disturbing or reorienting normative sexuality at all. Sometimes, gender ambiguity can operate precisely to contain or deflect non-normative sexual practice and thereby work to keep normative sexuality intact (p.xiv)”. Ada/Zsazsa is given the power to switch from being a homosexual male to a heterosexual female through the use of zaturannah, a magical stone that gives her powers. This stone becomes the deus ex machina for both the community and for Ada himself. Zaturannah is the key for Ada to literally be anyone he wants to be – a parlorista or a sexy female with super strength. It is through this magical switch that we can see what Butler is trying to imply in her work; gender ambiguity keeps normative sexuality intact in such a way that it affirms the said norm. Whether it be following the shallow “women are passive, men are aggressive” saying, the fact that ambiguities in gender still bounce back to this norm, affirms it.

Conclusion

Ada/Zsazsa is the combination of contrasts because her character is both a hero and a trickster, the two major types of characters, especially in the 1930s (Reyes, 158). Ada/Zsazsa also possessed both genders which implies that this ambiguity allows her to be more superior to other genders because she may choose which character to portray anytime. Zsazsa Zaturannah may be considered as a humorous epic, with a combination of archetypes used, which may imply that Carlo Vergara’s work is a medium that not serves as entertainment, more so, it proliferates liberation. Zsazsa Zaturannah is a hero that reflects how the LGBTQ community wants to be saved, to be freed and put to the same pedestal where Ada/Zsazsa is.

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